

Different Types of Magic Rectangles in Construction of Magic Squares of Orders 14 and 18

The work is also available at the following link:
<https://shorturl.at/KXY47>

Inder J. Taneja¹

Abstract

*This work brings magic squares of orders 14 and 18. These are constructed based on different types of **magic rectangles**. These types are **bordered, double digits** and **cornered magic rectangles**. For more details on these types of magic rectangles refer author's work [86]. The construction of magic squares is based on four equal sums **magic rectangles**. In case of **cornered magic rectangles**, three different types of magic squares are studied. Similar kind of work based on **bordered magic rectangles** or **double digits magic squares** can be seen in [67, 84]*

¹Formerly, Professor of Mathematics, Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil (1978-2012).
Also worked at Delhi University, India (1976-1978).
E-mail: ijaneja@gmail.com;
Web-sites: <http://inderjtaneja.com>; <http://numbers-magic.com>;
Twitter: @IJTANEJA; **Instagram:** @crazynumbers.

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1 Introduction

This work brings magic squares in very different way. These are based on cornered magic rectangles. First of let’s understand what we mean by cornered magic rectangles. There are normal magic rectangles with some extra properties. For examples if remove external border still we left with lower order cornered magic rectangles. Here the external border is understood as one half. See below few examples:

2 Different Type Magic Rectangles

Magic rectangles are well known in the literature. Below is an example of a **magic rectangle** of order 12×20 .

196	109	50	80	79	39	203	61	93	98	18	95	223	85	158	137	108	129	225	224	2410
142	240	154	74	150	73	30	11	120	37	121	46	66	236	218	180	174	166	110	62	2410
115	35	59	232	163	107	133	16	228	49	112	19	209	197	13	113	235	204	149	22	2410
54	24	135	185	117	220	141	145	6	201	202	186	156	51	194	81	119	53	106	34	2410
184	92	168	9	237	29	153	226	207	94	229	1	56	26	7	175	123	84	199	111	2410
12	43	128	136	5	173	138	216	105	78	214	160	144	99	44	114	89	116	231	165	2410
205	212	47	41	146	210	227	86	14	151	71	155	36	181	195	20	126	72	76	139	2410
100	187	217	208	147	177	67	127	27	183	104	77	60	233	191	45	125	42	2	91	2410
215	55	40	58	159	122	161	211	70	176	221	192	148	25	57	96	172	82	48	102	2410
200	206	189	3	198	131	4	33	239	101	21	222	32	178	38	152	65	193	75	130	2410
8	140	171	238	17	31	179	124	170	188	69	63	97	83	213	164	23	143	157	132	2410
15	103	88	182	28	134	10	190	167	90	64	230	219	52	118	169	87	162	68	234	2410
1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446

It is just a simple **magic rectangle**. Below there are three different types of **magic rectangles**:

1. **Bordered Magic Rectangles;**
2. **Double Digits Magic Rectangles;**
3. **Cornered Magic Rectangles.**

Later these types of magic rectangles are used to construct magic squares. The construction is based on four equal order and equal sums magic rectangles of each type. For details refer author’s work [86, 87, 88, 89]. These are given in following subsections. The examples considered in this work are calculated using softwares by H. White [1].

2.1 Bordered Magic Rectangles

Bordered magic rectangles are very much similar to **bordered magic squares**. The difference is that in case **bordered magic rectangles**, the width and height are different, while in case of **bordered magic squares** the width and height are the same. Below are few examples of **bordered magic rectangles**.

Let's consider a **bordered magic rectangle** of order 12×18 formed by 216 sequential entries, i.e., from 1 to 216:

8	210	198	5	202	207	21	26	204	194	197	28	1	25	200	9	206	12	1953
201	44	184	35	50	185	30	180	51	172	175	41	177	39	170	165	38	16	1953
215	49	56	66	148	158	57	149	147	157	163	65	55	67	159	72	168	2	1953
22	169	61	88	81	73	141	132	83	131	82	143	78	133	137	156	48	195	1953
14	34	155	140	90	97	95	128	118	96	94	126	124	117	77	62	183	203	1953
4	181	63	130	119	109	105	116	106	103	115	104	110	98	87	154	36	213	1953
24	43	153	75	125	108	112	101	111	114	102	113	107	92	142	64	174	193	1953
190	186	164	138	100	120	122	89	99	121	123	91	93	127	79	53	31	27	1953
6	29	71	80	136	144	76	85	134	86	135	74	139	84	129	146	188	211	1953
199	171	145	151	69	59	160	68	70	60	54	152	162	150	58	161	46	18	1953
214	179	33	182	167	32	187	37	166	45	42	176	40	178	47	52	173	3	1953
205	7	19	212	15	10	196	191	13	23	20	189	216	192	17	208	11	209	1953
1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302

According to colors the entries are as follows:

20	273	224	277	28	245	271	58	50	15	59	19	34	13	232	23	221	256	259	233	2810
8	261	57	4	253	36	10	223	231	266	222	262	247	268	49	258	60	25	48	22	2810
226	55	70	189	69	102	193	79	63	94	204	215	214	81	191	93	178	213	249	32	2810
237	44	92	211	212	179	88	202	218	187	77	66	67	200	90	188	68	103	251	30	2810
228	53	192	89	169	110	173	168	158	154	107	119	159	106	149	114	185	96	6	275	2810
252	29	201	80	171	112	108	113	123	127	174	162	122	175	167	132	84	197	243	38	2810
227	54	196	85	150	131	146	137	143	136	147	133	142	140	109	172	91	190	257	24	2810
26	255	186	95	117	164	135	144	138	145	134	148	139	141	156	125	194	87	2	279	2810
244	37	74	207	116	161	176	128	166	124	121	126	129	118	151	170	180	101	7	274	2810
229	52	209	72	120	165	105	153	115	157	160	155	152	163	111	130	64	217	27	254	2810
250	31	99	195	198	78	210	76	75	100	199	61	208	183	62	216	184	104	39	242	2810
16	265	86	182	83	203	71	205	206	181	82	220	73	98	219	65	177	97	269	12	2810
1	278	9	264	235	14	51	43	56	241	248	42	236	41	246	276	21	11	263	234	2810
3	280	272	17	46	267	230	238	225	40	33	239	45	240	35	5	260	270	47	18	2810
1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	

By double digits we understand that, except corners, all others rows or columns taken in pairs are of equal sums. Actually, these are **double digits bordered magic rectangles**, but for simplicity, we shall call it **double digits magic rectangles**. See below sums according to colors:

• **Horizontal Sums in Pairs**

224	277	28	245	271	58	50	15	59	19	34	13	232	23	221	256
57	4	253	36	10	223	231	266	222	262	247	268	49	258	60	25
281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281
9	264	235	14	51	43	56	241	248	42	236	41	246	276	21	11
272	17	46	267	230	238	225	40	33	239	45	240	35	5	260	270
281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281
69	102	193	79	63	94	204	215	214	81	191	93				
212	179	88	202	218	187	77	66	67	200	90	188				
281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281			
198	78	210	76	75	100	199	61	208	183	62	216				
83	203	71	205	206	181	82	220	73	98	219	65				
281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281			
173	168	158	154	107	119	159	106								
108	113	123	127	174	162	122	175								
281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281								
176	128	166	124	121	126	129	118								
105	153	115	157	160	155	152	163								
281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281								
146	137	143	136	147	133	142	140								
135	144	138	145	134	148	139	141								
281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281								

• **Vertical Sums in Pairs**

226	55	281	249	32	281	192	89	281	185	96	281
237	44	281	251	30	281	201	80	281	84	197	281
228	53	281	6	275	281	196	85	281	91	190	281
252	29	281	243	38	281	186	95	281	194	87	281
227	54	281	257	24	281	74	207	281	180	101	281
26	255	281	2	279	281	209	72	281	64	217	281
244	37	281	7	274	281						
229	52	281	27	254	281	150	131	281	109	172	281
250	31	281	39	242	281	117	164	281	156	125	281
16	265	281	269	12	281						

More detail on **double digits magic rectangles** refer [86]. There are many magic squares are constructed based on this idea. See the

author’s work [67, 68, 69, 70, 71, 72]. Magic squares of orders 7 to 108 can be seen in [81].

2.3 Cornered Magic Rectangle

Let’s consider a **cornered magic rectangle** of order 10×24 formed by 240 sequential entries, i.e., from 1 to 240:

115	113	135	124	136	116	110	111	109	133	129	119	123	107	127	121	98	143	167	74	206	35	8	233	2892
126	128	106	117	105	125	131	130	132	108	112	122	118	134	114	120	90	151	77	164	36	205	229	12	2892
141	96	92	139	154	101	144	99	91	103	88	137	156	86	152	147	148	95	76	165	57	184	213	28	2892
100	145	149	102	87	140	97	142	150	138	153	104	85	155	89	94	146	93	174	67	198	43	27	214	2892
173	177	175	73	83	180	62	63	71	84	171	163	166	161	72	162	159	65	69	81	202	39	209	32	2892
68	64	66	168	158	61	179	178	170	157	70	78	75	80	169	79	82	176	160	172	34	207	240	1	2892
48	197	182	188	55	190	196	54	40	58	46	56	200	191	181	33	38	52	49	199	194	204	224	17	2892
193	44	59	53	186	51	45	187	201	183	195	185	41	50	60	208	203	189	192	42	37	47	25	216	2892
13	5	239	231	6	237	20	220	26	30	227	11	15	219	16	238	31	217	223	9	212	222	7	218	2892
228	236	2	10	235	4	221	21	215	211	14	230	226	22	225	3	210	24	18	232	29	19	23	234	2892
1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205

In this case the distribution is $D_{10 \times 24} := \{1, 2, \dots, 240\}$. Except the corners, the numbers are of equal sums in pairs. Distributions in colors as follows:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
209	210	211	212	213	214	215	216	217	218	219	220	221	222	223	224	225	226	227	228	229	230	231	232	233	234	235	236	237	238	239	240
33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60				
181	182	183	184	185	186	187	188	189	190	191	192	193	194	195	196	197	198	199	200	201	202	203	204	205	206	207	208				
61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	84								
157	158	159	160	161	162	163	164	165	166	167	168	169	170	171	172	173	174	175	176	177	178	179	180								
85	86	87	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	96	97	98	99	100	101	102	103	104												
137	138	139	140	141	142	143	144	145	146	147	148	149	150	151	152	153	154	155	156												
115	105	106	107	108	109	110	111	112	113	114	116	117	118	119	120																
121	122	123	124	125	126	127	128	129	130	131	132	133	134	135	136																

Except the last entries, the others are known by **half-sequential** entries.

More detail on **cornered magic rectangles** refer [86]. Few work on magic squares connected with **cornered magic rectangles** can be seen in [82, 83, 84, 85].

The aim of this work is to write magic squares of orders 14 and 18 using four equal sums different types of magic rectangles.

3 Magic Squares of Order 14

Initially, let's write two basic magic squares of order 14. These are known by **double digits** and **cornered magic squares** of order 14:

1	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.com/ @IJTANEJA													1379
1	3	195	193	192	191	7	8	9	187	11	185	13	184	1379
196	194	2	4	5	6	190	189	188	10	186	12	15	182	1379
37	160	51	49	147	145	144	54	142	56	57	140	183	14	1379
159	38	146	148	50	52	53	143	55	141	59	138	181	16	1379
39	158	73	124	81	115	114	113	82	86	139	58	180	17	1379
157	40	123	74	110	88	108	89	91	105	137	60	179	18	1379
156	41	75	122	104	103	95	96	100	93	136	61	19	178	1379
155	42	121	76	98	94	101	102	97	99	62	135	20	177	1379
43	154	120	77	87	106	90	107	109	92	134	63	21	176	1379
44	153	118	79	111	85	83	84	112	116	64	133	175	22	1379
45	152	80	117	65	131	67	129	72	70	126	128	23	174	1379
47	150	78	119	132	66	130	68	125	127	71	69	173	24	1379
151	46	25	171	27	169	168	167	31	32	33	35	163	161	1379
149	48	172	26	170	28	29	30	166	165	164	162	34	36	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

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97	102	91	104	83	114	77	120	132	65	169	28	192	5	1379
92	103	98	101	111	86	117	80	66	131	149	48	183	14	1379
106	93	100	95	115	82	130	67	60	137	159	38	13	184	1379
99	96	105	94	88	109	123	74	134	63	45	152	171	26	1379
113	81	112	108	87	90	72	125	51	146	158	39	178	19	1379
84	116	85	89	107	110	69	128	139	58	150	47	11	186	1379
79	70	68	126	122	78	124	121	61	136	164	33	7	190	1379
118	127	129	71	75	119	76	73	144	53	40	157	23	174	1379
49	64	50	62	145	54	140	138	142	141	42	155	25	172	1379
148	133	147	135	52	143	57	59	56	55	31	166	17	180	1379
46	27	35	168	167	153	163	41	160	36	32	154	189	8	1379
151	170	162	29	30	44	34	156	37	161	43	165	182	15	1379
194	187	16	1	177	195	6	21	24	12	4	175	179	188	1379
3	10	181	196	20	2	191	176	173	185	193	22	9	18	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

3.1 Magic Squares of Order 14 with Bordered Magic Rectangles

Below are few examples of magic squares of order 14 constructed with four equal sums **bordered magic rectangles**. These are centered with magic squares of order 6.

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7	185	188	2	8	193	10	6	194	192	25	176	166	27	1379
196	183	182	16	179	20	13	17	178	1	32	159	38	165	1379
186	14	15	181	18	177	184	180	19	11	29	37	160	168	1379
5	12	9	195	189	4	187	191	3	190	175	36	161	22	1379
67	136	126	65	81	115	114	113	82	86	169	163	34	28	1379
125	119	78	72	110	88	108	89	91	105	24	33	164	173	1379
128	80	117	69	104	103	95	96	100	93	167	162	35	30	1379
66	77	120	131	98	94	101	102	97	99	171	40	157	26	1379
68	118	79	129	87	106	90	107	109	92	23	158	39	174	1379
133	73	124	64	111	85	83	84	112	116	170	21	31	172	1379
62	122	75	135	150	52	49	151	149	44	147	155	43	45	1379
70	76	121	127	41	57	60	56	143	53	138	139	142	156	1379
134	123	74	63	51	140	137	141	54	144	59	58	55	146	1379
132	61	71	130	152	145	148	46	48	153	50	42	154	47	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

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7	185	188	2	8	193	10	6	194	192	25	176	166	27	1379
196	183	182	16	179	20	13	17	178	1	32	159	38	165	1379
186	14	15	181	18	177	184	180	19	11	29	37	160	168	1379
5	12	9	195	189	4	187	191	3	190	175	36	161	22	1379
67	136	126	65	86	110	83	116	84	112	169	163	34	28	1379
125	119	78	72	115	97	102	91	104	82	24	33	164	173	1379
128	80	117	69	109	92	103	98	101	88	167	162	35	30	1379
66	77	120	131	107	106	93	100	95	90	171	40	157	26	1379
68	118	79	129	89	99	96	105	94	108	23	158	39	174	1379
133	73	124	64	85	87	114	81	113	111	170	21	31	172	1379
62	122	75	135	150	52	49	151	149	44	147	155	43	45	1379
70	76	121	127	41	57	60	56	143	53	138	139	142	156	1379
134	123	74	63	51	140	137	141	54	144	59	58	55	146	1379
132	61	71	130	152	145	148	46	48	153	50	42	154	47	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

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7	185	188	2	8	193	10	6	194	192	25	176	166	27	1379
196	183	182	16	179	20	13	17	178	1	32	159	38	165	1379
186	14	15	181	18	177	184	180	19	11	29	37	160	168	1379
5	12	9	195	189	4	187	191	3	190	175	36	161	22	1379
67	136	126	65	104	97	102	96	94	98	169	163	34	28	1379
125	119	78	72	87	111	85	113	114	81	24	33	164	173	1379
128	80	117	69	109	107	89	92	106	88	167	162	35	30	1379
66	77	120	131	82	90	108	105	91	115	171	40	157	26	1379
68	118	79	129	116	86	112	84	83	110	23	158	39	174	1379
133	73	124	64	93	100	95	101	103	99	170	21	31	172	1379
62	122	75	135	150	52	49	151	149	44	147	155	43	45	1379
70	76	121	127	41	57	60	56	143	53	138	139	142	156	1379
134	123	74	63	51	140	137	141	54	144	59	58	55	146	1379
132	61	71	130	152	145	148	46	48	153	50	42	154	47	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

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7	185	188	2	8	193	10	6	194	192	25	176	166	27	1379
196	183	182	16	179	20	13	17	178	1	32	159	38	165	1379
186	14	15	181	18	177	184	180	19	11	29	37	160	168	1379
5	12	9	195	189	4	187	191	3	190	175	36	161	22	1379
67	136	126	65	97	102	91	104	109	88	169	163	34	28	1379
125	119	78	72	92	103	98	101	107	90	24	33	164	173	1379
128	80	117	69	106	93	100	95	115	82	167	162	35	30	1379
66	77	120	131	99	96	105	94	89	108	171	40	157	26	1379
68	118	79	129	84	83	116	110	86	112	23	158	39	174	1379
133	73	124	64	113	114	81	87	85	111	170	21	31	172	1379
62	122	75	135	150	52	49	151	149	44	147	155	43	45	1379
70	76	121	127	41	57	60	56	143	53	138	139	142	156	1379
134	123	74	63	51	140	137	141	54	144	59	58	55	146	1379
132	61	71	130	152	145	148	46	48	153	50	42	154	47	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

3.2 Magic Squares of Order 14 with Cornered Magic Rectangles

We have written in two different styles magic squares of order 14 using 4 equal sums **cornered magic rectangles**. These are centered with magic squares of order 6. These are of two different types. See below these examples.

3.2.1 First Type

3	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.com/	@IJTANEJA	1379									
181	15	14	184	17	178	20	179	9	188	28	169	33	164	1379
16	182	183	13	180	19	177	18	192	5	27	170	40	157	1379
194	7	12	1	186	195	4	8	187	191	165	32	159	38	1379
3	190	185	196	11	2	193	189	6	10	174	23	162	35	1379
133	66	69	126	81	115	114	113	82	86	21	176	39	158	1379
64	131	71	128	110	88	108	89	91	105	175	22	161	36	1379
124	73	129	68	104	103	95	96	100	93	173	24	160	37	1379
119	78	125	72	98	94	101	102	97	99	166	31	34	163	1379
74	123	130	67	87	106	90	107	109	92	26	167	29	172	1379
117	80	61	136	111	85	83	84	112	116	30	171	168	25	1379
77	120	132	65	50	52	149	148	156	44	47	146	42	151	1379
79	118	70	127	145	147	48	49	41	153	150	51	155	46	1379
76	121	135	62	154	43	54	144	139	141	57	55	60	138	1379
122	75	63	134	45	152	143	53	58	56	140	142	137	59	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

4	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.com/	@IJTANEJA	1379									
181	15	14	184	17	178	20	179	9	188	28	169	33	164	1379
16	182	183	13	180	19	177	18	192	5	27	170	40	157	1379
194	7	12	1	186	195	4	8	187	191	165	32	159	38	1379
3	190	185	196	11	2	193	189	6	10	174	23	162	35	1379
133	66	69	126	86	110	83	116	84	112	21	176	39	158	1379
64	131	71	128	115	97	102	91	104	82	175	22	161	36	1379
124	73	129	68	109	92	103	98	101	88	173	24	160	37	1379
119	78	125	72	107	106	93	100	95	90	166	31	34	163	1379
74	123	130	67	89	99	96	105	94	108	26	167	29	172	1379
117	80	61	136	85	87	114	81	113	111	30	171	168	25	1379
77	120	132	65	50	52	149	148	156	44	47	146	42	151	1379
79	118	70	127	145	147	48	49	41	153	150	51	155	46	1379
76	121	135	62	154	43	54	144	139	141	57	55	60	138	1379
122	75	63	134	45	152	143	53	58	56	140	142	137	59	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

5	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.com/	@IJTANEJA	1379									
181	15	14	184	17	178	20	179	9	188	28	169	33	164	1379
16	182	183	13	180	19	177	18	192	5	27	170	40	157	1379
194	7	12	1	186	195	4	8	187	191	165	32	159	38	1379
3	190	185	196	11	2	193	189	6	10	174	23	162	35	1379
133	66	69	126	104	97	102	96	94	98	21	176	39	158	1379
64	131	71	128	87	111	85	113	114	81	175	22	161	36	1379
124	73	129	68	109	107	89	92	106	88	173	24	160	37	1379
119	78	125	72	82	90	108	105	91	115	166	31	34	163	1379
74	123	130	67	116	86	112	84	83	110	26	167	29	172	1379
117	80	61	136	93	100	95	101	103	99	30	171	168	25	1379
77	120	132	65	50	52	149	148	156	44	47	146	42	151	1379
79	118	70	127	145	147	48	49	41	153	150	51	155	46	1379
76	121	135	62	154	43	54	144	139	141	57	55	60	138	1379
122	75	63	134	45	152	143	53	58	56	140	142	137	59	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

6	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.com/	@IJTANEJA	1379									
181	15	14	184	17	178	20	179	9	188	28	169	33	164	1379
16	182	183	13	180	19	177	18	192	5	27	170	40	157	1379
194	7	12	1	186	195	4	8	187	191	165	32	159	38	1379
3	190	185	196	11	2	193	189	6	10	174	23	162	35	1379
133	66	69	126	97	102	91	104	109	88	21	176	39	158	1379
64	131	71	128	92	103	98	101	107	90	175	22	161	36	1379
124	73	129	68	106	93	100	95	115	82	173	24	160	37	1379
119	78	125	72	99	96	105	94	89	108	166	31	34	163	1379
74	123	130	67	84	83	116	110	86	112	26	167	29	172	1379
117	80	61	136	113	114	81	87	85	111	30	171	168	25	1379
77	120	132	65	50	52	149	148	156	44	47	146	42	151	1379
79	118	70	127	145	147	48	49	41	153	150	51	155	46	1379
76	121	135	62	154	43	54	144	139	141	57	55	60	138	1379
122	75	63	134	45	152	143	53	58	56	140	142	137	59	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

3.2.2 Second Type

7	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.com/	@IJTANEJA	1379									
8	7	195	194	1	185	193	186	6	10	158	39	174	23	1379
189	190	2	3	196	12	4	11	187	191	35	162	32	165	1379
13	20	179	182	19	181	180	14	9	188	34	163	27	170	1379
184	177	18	15	178	16	17	183	192	5	164	33	24	173	1379
70	125	134	65	81	115	114	113	82	86	37	160	166	31	1379
72	127	63	132	110	88	108	89	91	105	161	36	175	22	1379
129	68	74	123	104	103	95	96	100	93	40	157	21	176	1379
128	69	118	79	98	94	101	102	97	99	159	38	28	169	1379
131	66	119	78	87	106	90	107	109	92	29	172	167	26	1379
67	130	121	76	111	85	83	84	112	116	168	25	171	30	1379
64	133	75	122	153	44	144	139	56	137	54	59	57	142	1379
62	135	77	120	46	151	53	58	141	60	143	138	140	55	1379
126	71	80	117	49	51	149	145	150	155	152	41	50	43	1379
136	61	124	73	146	148	48	52	47	42	45	156	147	154	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

8	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.com/	@IJTANEJA	1379									
8	7	195	194	1	185	193	186	6	10	158	39	174	23	1379
189	190	2	3	196	12	4	11	187	191	35	162	32	165	1379
13	20	179	182	19	181	180	14	9	188	34	163	27	170	1379
184	177	18	15	178	16	17	183	192	5	164	33	24	173	1379
70	125	134	65	86	110	83	116	84	112	37	160	166	31	1379
72	127	63	132	115	97	102	91	104	82	161	36	175	22	1379
129	68	74	123	109	92	103	98	101	88	40	157	21	176	1379
128	69	118	79	107	106	93	100	95	90	159	38	28	169	1379
131	66	119	78	89	99	96	105	94	108	29	172	167	26	1379
67	130	121	76	85	87	114	81	113	111	168	25	171	30	1379
64	133	75	122	153	44	144	139	56	137	54	59	57	142	1379
62	135	77	120	46	151	53	58	141	60	143	138	140	55	1379
126	71	80	117	49	51	149	145	150	155	152	41	50	43	1379
136	61	124	73	146	148	48	52	47	42	45	156	147	154	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

9	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.com/	@IJTANEJA	1379									
8	7	195	194	1	185	193	186	6	10	158	39	174	23	1379
189	190	2	3	196	12	4	11	187	191	35	162	32	165	1379
13	20	179	182	19	181	180	14	9	188	34	163	27	170	1379
184	177	18	15	178	16	17	183	192	5	164	33	24	173	1379
70	125	134	65	104	97	102	96	94	98	37	160	166	31	1379
72	127	63	132	87	111	85	113	114	81	161	36	175	22	1379
129	68	74	123	109	107	89	92	106	88	40	157	21	176	1379
128	69	118	79	82	90	108	105	91	115	159	38	28	169	1379
131	66	119	78	116	86	112	84	83	110	29	172	167	26	1379
67	130	121	76	93	100	95	101	103	99	168	25	171	30	1379
64	133	75	122	153	44	144	139	56	137	54	59	57	142	1379
62	135	77	120	46	151	53	58	141	60	143	138	140	55	1379
126	71	80	117	49	51	149	145	150	155	152	41	50	43	1379
136	61	124	73	146	148	48	52	47	42	45	156	147	154	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

10	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.com/	@IJTANEJA	1379									
8	7	195	194	1	185	193	186	6	10	158	39	174	23	1379
189	190	2	3	196	12	4	11	187	191	35	162	32	165	1379
13	20	179	182	19	181	180	14	9	188	34	163	27	170	1379
184	177	18	15	178	16	17	183	192	5	164	33	24	173	1379
70	125	134	65	97	102	91	104	109	88	37	160	166	31	1379
72	127	63	132	92	103	98	101	107	90	161	36	175	22	1379
129	68	74	123	106	93	100	95	115	82	40	157	21	176	1379
128	69	118	79	99	96	105	94	89	108	159	38	28	169	1379
131	66	119	78	84	83	116	110	86	112	29	172	167	26	1379
67	130	121	76	113	114	81	87	85	111	168	25	171	30	1379
64	133	75	122	153	44	144	139	56	137	54	59	57	142	1379
62	135	77	120	46	151	53	58	141	60	143	138	140	55	1379
126	71	80	117	49	51	149	145	150	155	152	41	50	43	1379
136	61	124	73	146	148	48	52	47	42	45	156	147	154	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

Remark 1. In this case are unable to write magic squares of order 14 using **double digits magic rectangles**.

4 Magic Squares of Order 18

Initially, let's write two basic magic squares of order 18. These are known by **double digits** and **cornered magic squares** of order 18:

1	Inder J. Taneja																https://inderjtaneja.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	2925
1	3	323	321	320	6	318	8	9	315	11	313	312	14	310	16	17	308	2925		
324	322	2	4	5	319	7	317	316	10	314	12	13	311	15	309	19	306	2925		
49	276	65	67	259	257	256	255	71	72	73	251	75	249	77	248	307	18	2925		
275	50	260	258	66	68	69	70	254	253	252	74	250	76	79	246	305	20	2925		
51	274	101	224	115	113	211	209	208	118	206	120	121	204	247	78	304	21	2925		
273	52	223	102	210	212	114	116	117	207	119	205	123	202	245	80	22	303	2925		
272	53	103	222	137	188	145	179	178	177	146	150	203	122	244	81	302	23	2925		
54	271	221	104	187	138	174	152	172	153	155	169	201	124	243	82	24	301	2925		
270	55	220	105	139	186	168	167	159	160	164	157	200	125	83	242	25	300	2925		
56	269	219	106	185	140	162	158	165	166	161	163	126	199	84	241	299	26	2925		
57	268	107	218	184	141	151	170	154	171	173	156	198	127	85	240	27	298	2925		
267	58	108	217	182	143	175	149	147	148	176	180	128	197	239	86	297	28	2925		
59	266	109	216	144	181	129	195	131	193	136	134	190	192	87	238	296	29	2925		
265	60	111	214	142	183	196	130	194	132	189	191	135	133	237	88	30	295	2925		
264	61	215	110	89	235	91	233	232	231	95	96	97	99	227	225	294	31	2925		
262	63	213	112	236	90	234	92	93	94	230	229	228	226	98	100	32	293	2925		
64	261	33	291	35	289	288	38	286	40	41	283	43	281	280	278	48	46	2925		
62	263	292	34	290	36	37	287	39	285	284	42	282	44	45	47	277	279	2925		
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	

2	Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA				2925		
161	166	155	168	178	147	181	144	204	121	226	99	85	240	61	264	28	297	2925	
156	167	162	165	177	148	142	183	207	118	221	104	66	259	281	44	312	13	2925	
170	157	164	159	146	179	140	185	126	199	219	106	71	254	270	55	34	291	2925	
163	160	169	158	150	175	135	190	115	210	105	220	255	70	46	279	11	314	2925	
153	145	176	154	173	174	137	188	125	200	213	112	83	242	262	63	3	322	2925	
172	180	149	171	151	152	186	139	212	113	108	217	74	251	64	261	33	292	2925	
132	189	131	143	191	184	192	138	114	211	223	102	252	73	282	43	296	29	2925	
193	136	194	182	134	141	187	133	202	123	109	216	81	244	273	52	18	307	2925	
127	117	203	197	195	209	205	129	119	124	233	92	247	78	286	39	308	17	2925	
198	208	122	128	130	116	120	196	201	206	98	227	245	80	35	290	305	20	2925	
111	91	224	107	215	94	96	228	232	222	100	230	237	88	38	287	302	23	2925	
214	234	101	218	110	231	229	97	93	103	95	225	82	243	263	62	318	7	2925	
90	239	248	67	68	246	250	249	89	260	72	87	241	69	40	285	19	306	2925	
235	86	77	258	257	79	75	76	236	65	253	238	256	84	59	266	304	21	2925	
45	36	288	47	41	54	267	276	53	274	60	275	277	56	283	268	311	14	2925	
280	289	37	278	284	271	58	49	272	51	265	50	48	269	57	42	1	324	2925	
22	16	319	5	24	9	323	300	8	32	321	294	313	310	26	10	295	298	2925	
303	309	6	320	301	316	2	25	317	293	4	31	12	15	299	315	27	30	2925	
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

4.1 Magic Squares of Order 18 with Bordered Magic Rectangles

Below are examples of magic squares of order 18 centered in magic squares of order 6 and 10 respectively. These are constructed with four equal sums bordered magic rectangles of orders 6×12 and 4×14 .

4	Inder J. Taneja	https://inderjtaneja.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	2925														
13	1	323	310	311	16	11	317	321	315	3	9	45	41	283	48	282	276	2925	
320	297	25	19	24	20	299	308	307	304	22	5	37	58	262	266	64	288	2925	
6	27	29	295	292	289	32	34	35	294	298	319	52	61	256	69	264	273	2925	
313	23	296	30	33	36	293	291	290	31	302	12	274	60	253	72	265	51	2925	
7	303	300	306	301	305	26	17	18	21	28	318	275	55	259	66	270	50	2925	
316	324	2	15	14	309	314	8	4	10	322	312	287	56	70	255	269	38	2925	
121	212	114	205	115	208	150	174	147	180	148	176	47	263	68	257	62	278	2925	
109	189	135	131	195	216	179	161	166	155	168	146	281	272	65	260	53	44	2925	
124	133	142	183	192	201	173	156	167	162	165	152	285	271	71	254	54	40	2925	
202	132	181	144	193	123	171	170	157	164	159	154	279	268	258	67	57	46	2925	
203	127	184	141	198	122	153	163	160	169	158	172	39	261	63	59	267	286	2925	
215	128	187	138	197	110	149	151	178	145	177	175	49	284	42	277	43	280	2925	
119	191	140	185	134	206	85	83	88	238	239	251	73	245	249	243	75	81	2925	
209	200	137	188	125	116	248	225	97	96	91	92	227	236	235	232	94	77	2925	
213	199	143	182	126	112	78	99	106	217	220	223	222	107	101	104	226	247	2925	
207	196	186	139	129	118	241	95	219	108	105	102	103	218	224	221	230	84	2925	
111	130	190	194	136	214	79	231	228	229	234	233	98	89	90	93	100	246	2925	
117	113	211	120	210	204	244	242	237	87	86	74	252	80	76	82	250	240	2925	
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

29	Inder J. Taneja	https://inderjtaneja.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	2925													
13	6	315	313	317	310	1	3	16	5	321	323	14	318	41	286	288	35	2925
314	297	22	300	23	26	307	301	20	17	304	306	27	11	34	45	280	291	2925
316	28	303	25	302	299	18	24	305	308	21	19	298	9	287	50	275	38	2925
7	319	10	12	8	15	324	322	309	320	4	2	311	312	285	272	53	40	2925
97	230	232	91	203	198	128	196	130	126	116	210	114	204	289	51	274	36	2925
90	213	112	235	125	138	132	192	194	181	143	183	137	200	282	54	271	43	2925
231	106	219	94	201	135	176	174	147	180	148	150	190	124	29	279	46	296	2925
229	216	109	96	123	136	146	161	166	155	168	179	189	202	31	273	52	294	2925
233	222	103	92	208	141	152	156	167	162	165	173	184	117	44	48	277	281	2925
226	111	214	99	113	191	154	170	157	164	159	171	134	212	33	269	56	292	2925
85	223	102	240	205	186	172	163	160	169	158	153	139	120	293	276	49	32	2925
87	217	108	238	119	185	175	151	178	145	177	149	140	206	295	278	47	30	2925
100	104	221	225	207	188	193	133	131	144	182	142	187	118	42	55	270	283	2925
89	101	224	236	121	127	197	129	195	199	209	115	211	122	290	39	37	284	2925
237	220	105	88	69	62	259	257	261	254	57	59	72	61	265	267	70	262	2925
239	107	218	86	258	241	78	244	83	82	251	245	76	73	248	79	250	67	2925
98	110	215	227	260	84	247	81	242	243	74	80	249	252	77	246	75	65	2925
234	95	93	228	63	263	66	68	64	71	268	266	253	264	60	58	255	256	2925
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

For more examples of similar kind with pdf file for download refer the author’s site <https://shorturl.at/KXY47>.

4.2 Magic Squares of Order 18 with Double Digits Magic Rectangles

Below is a magic square of order 18 centered in magic squares of order 6. It is constructed with four equal sums double digits magic rectangles of order 6×12 .

7	Inder J. Taneja		https://inderjtaneja.com/		https://numbers-magic.com/		@IJTANEJA		2925										
297	22	25	19	24	20	299	308	307	304	320	5	37	288	262	266	58	64	2925	
303	28	300	306	301	305	26	17	18	21	6	319	52	273	63	59	261	267	2925	
27	298	295	294	292	289	32	34	35	29	313	12	274	51	65	260	61	264	2925	
23	302	30	31	33	36	293	291	290	296	7	318	275	50	256	69	60	265	2925	
1	323	310	311	16	11	317	321	315	3	13	9	285	40	259	66	55	270	2925	
324	2	15	14	309	314	8	4	10	322	316	312	47	278	70	255	56	269	2925	
189	195	135	131	109	216	145	179	178	177	146	150	281	44	68	257	263	62	2925	
130	136	190	194	124	201	174	152	172	153	155	169	287	38	253	72	272	53	2925	
133	192	142	183	202	123	168	167	159	160	164	157	279	46	71	254	271	54	2925	
132	193	181	144	203	122	162	158	165	166	161	163	39	286	258	67	268	57	2925	
127	198	184	141	215	110	151	170	154	171	173	156	45	276	48	282	41	283	2925	
128	197	187	138	119	206	175	149	147	148	176	180	49	280	277	43	284	42	2925	
191	134	140	185	111	214	225	94	97	96	91	92	227	236	235	232	248	77	2925	
200	125	137	188	213	112	231	100	228	229	234	233	98	89	90	93	78	247	2925	
199	126	143	182	207	118	99	226	106	217	220	223	222	101	107	104	241	84	2925	
196	129	186	139	209	116	95	230	219	108	105	102	103	224	218	221	79	246	2925	
212	114	205	115	121	208	83	88	238	239	251	73	245	249	243	75	85	81	2925	
113	211	120	210	117	204	242	237	87	86	74	252	80	76	82	250	244	240	2925	
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

For more examples of similar kind with pdf file for download refer the author’s site <https://shorturl.at/KXY47>.

4.3 Magic Squares of Order 18 with Cornered Magic Rectangles

We have written in three different styles magic squares of order 18 using 4 equal sums **cornered magic rectangles**. These are centered with magic squares of order 6 and 10. See below these examples.

4.3.1 First Type

Below are examples of magic squares of order 18 centered in magic squares of order 6 and 10 respectively. These are constructed with four equal sums cornered magic rectangles of orders 6×12 and 4×14 .

14	Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA				2925		
	291	36	290	33	30	293	31	296	305	20	321	4	286	39	61	264	71	254	2925
	34	289	35	292	295	32	294	29	18	307	311	14	287	38	270	55	255	70	2925
	26	304	17	27	24	22	306	297	302	300	7	318	276	49	53	272	258	67	2925
	299	21	308	298	301	303	19	28	25	23	5	320	41	284	62	263	68	257	2925
	8	319	315	313	16	314	2	324	312	15	9	3	288	37	269	56	253	72	2925
	317	6	10	12	309	11	323	1	13	310	322	316	42	283	271	54	69	256	2925
	211	202	214	112	115	121	161	166	155	168	173	152	43	282	262	63	260	65	2925
	114	123	111	213	204	210	156	167	162	165	171	154	44	281	261	64	66	259	2925
	126	136	195	193	118	207	170	157	164	159	179	146	274	51	59	268	265	58	2925
	199	189	132	130	215	110	163	160	169	158	153	172	52	273	57	266	60	267	2925
	137	188	134	191	208	117	148	147	180	174	150	176	277	285	275	46	45	47	2925
	187	138	200	125	120	205	177	178	145	151	149	175	40	48	50	279	280	278	2925
	181	144	192	133	124	201	73	87	76	247	250	241	244	82	246	77	239	88	2925
	184	141	127	198	116	209	238	252	249	78	75	84	81	243	79	248	86	237	2925
	140	185	128	197	203	122	245	80	96	94	226	90	236	93	234	233	95	228	2925
	186	139	190	135	212	113	251	74	231	229	99	235	89	232	91	92	230	97	2925
	143	182	131	194	206	119	85	240	225	100	104	102	224	105	219	222	107	217	2925
	142	183	196	129	109	216	83	242	98	227	221	223	101	220	106	103	218	108	2925
	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

36	Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA				2925		
28	17	304	302	299	27	20	301	18	306	25	303	320	5	40	285	48	277	2925	
297	308	21	23	26	298	305	24	307	19	300	22	3	322	281	44	280	45	2925	
314	321	6	8	323	1	14	310	12	10	13	309	318	316	293	32	270	55	2925	
11	4	319	317	2	324	311	15	313	315	312	16	9	7	34	291	276	49	2925	
92	237	89	232	161	166	155	168	173	152	143	182	130	195	42	283	278	47	2925	
233	88	93	236	156	167	162	165	153	172	131	194	117	208	292	33	46	279	2925	
214	111	99	226	170	157	164	159	171	154	184	141	206	119	289	36	274	51	2925	
103	222	98	227	163	160	169	158	179	146	139	186	211	114	288	37	269	56	2925	
220	105	235	90	148	147	174	180	150	176	137	188	207	118	29	296	50	275	2925	
106	219	230	95	177	178	151	145	149	175	183	142	122	203	43	282	53	272	2925	
112	213	86	239	140	138	192	181	136	191	190	132	200	125	290	35	52	273	2925	
221	104	225	100	185	187	133	144	189	134	193	135	120	205	284	41	54	271	2925	
215	110	238	87	127	196	124	202	121	210	209	197	113	126	31	286	38	295	2925	
109	216	229	96	198	129	201	123	204	115	116	128	199	212	39	294	287	30	2925	
217	108	91	234	258	59	255	267	63	261	65	66	264	254	60	68	72	263	2925	
107	218	240	85	266	67	70	58	262	64	260	259	61	71	265	257	253	62	2925	
224	101	94	231	69	256	80	81	78	73	251	249	84	75	246	248	242	243	2925	
102	223	228	97	57	268	245	244	247	252	74	76	241	250	79	77	83	82	2925	
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

4.3.2 Second Type

Below is an example of magic square of order 18 centered in magic squares of order 6. It is constructed with four equal sums cornered magic rectangles of orders 6×12 .

15	Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA				2925		
4	321	18	307	29	295	289	292	32	35	294	34	37	274	281	287	49	47	2925	
310	15	28	297	296	30	36	33	293	290	31	291	51	288	44	38	276	278	2925	
322	3	303	24	26	298	300	19	20	308	23	304	40	285	60	267	261	62	2925	
319	6	301	22	299	27	25	306	305	17	302	21	283	42	58	265	64	263	2925	
7	312	10	323	316	12	16	8	311	320	314	1	275	50	262	63	68	257	2925	
13	318	315	2	9	313	309	317	14	5	11	324	277	48	54	271	71	254	2925	
183	142	134	191	116	209	145	179	178	177	146	150	280	45	272	53	253	72	2925	
144	181	196	129	211	114	174	152	172	153	155	169	46	279	57	268	69	256	2925	
182	143	125	200	207	118	168	167	159	160	164	157	282	43	269	56	260	65	2925	
141	184	135	190	205	120	162	158	165	166	161	163	41	284	270	55	258	67	2925	
138	187	132	193	124	201	151	170	154	171	173	156	286	39	59	266	255	70	2925	
185	140	130	195	204	121	175	149	147	148	176	180	52	273	264	61	66	259	2925	
139	186	198	127	206	119	250	251	240	77	252	78	80	79	238	88	241	76	2925	
188	137	189	136	216	109	75	74	85	248	73	247	245	246	87	237	249	84	2925	
197	126	194	133	110	215	98	234	89	97	233	235	226	225	95	93	239	86	2925	
128	199	192	131	123	202	227	91	236	228	92	90	99	100	232	230	81	244	2925	
213	203	115	113	117	214	219	102	222	104	217	105	224	107	229	96	83	242	2925	
112	122	210	212	111	208	106	223	103	221	108	220	101	218	94	231	82	243	2925	
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

4.3.3 Third Type

Below are examples of magic squares of order 18 centered in magic squares of order 6 and 10 respectively. These are constructed with four equal sums cornered magic rectangles of orders 6×12 and 4×14 .

22	Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA				2925		
322	323	312	5	324	6	7	8	310	16	313	4	257	68	62	263	52	273	2925	
3	2	13	320	1	319	318	317	15	309	321	12	72	253	268	57	38	287	2925	
26	306	17	25	305	307	298	297	23	21	311	14	254	71	53	272	279	46	2925	
299	19	308	300	20	18	27	28	304	302	10	315	69	256	63	262	277	48	2925	
291	30	294	32	289	296	33	35	301	24	9	316	66	259	60	265	44	281	2925	
34	295	31	293	36	29	292	290	22	303	11	314	255	70	58	267	278	47	2925	
109	202	209	215	121	119	161	166	155	168	173	152	67	258	270	55	283	42	2925	
123	216	116	110	204	206	156	167	162	165	171	154	260	65	261	64	288	37	2925	
112	213	132	195	189	134	170	157	164	159	179	146	269	54	266	61	276	49	2925	
211	114	130	193	136	191	163	160	169	158	153	172	56	271	264	59	51	274	2925	
214	111	190	135	140	185	148	147	180	174	150	176	285	275	43	41	45	286	2925	
205	120	126	199	143	182	177	178	145	151	149	175	40	50	282	284	39	280	2925	
208	117	200	125	181	144	247	78	90	235	101	220	217	223	104	107	222	106	2925	
118	207	129	196	141	184	238	87	100	225	224	105	108	102	221	218	103	219	2925	
210	115	197	128	188	137	250	75	231	96	98	226	228	91	92	236	95	232	2925	
113	212	131	194	186	139	76	249	229	94	227	99	97	234	233	89	230	93	2925	
203	122	198	127	183	142	79	240	82	251	244	84	88	80	242	248	239	73	2925	
124	201	192	133	138	187	85	246	243	74	81	241	237	245	83	77	86	252	2925	
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

53	Inder J. Taneja		https://inderjtaneja.com/		https://numbers-magic.com/		@IJTANEJA		2925										
321	309	6	320	14	12	317	316	1	15	318	312	3	11	56	269	286	39	2925	
4	16	319	5	311	313	8	9	324	310	7	13	314	322	271	54	293	32	2925	
20	298	308	297	306	18	302	304	22	25	24	26	10	315	276	49	36	289	2925	
305	27	17	28	19	307	23	21	303	300	301	299	323	2	274	51	34	291	2925	
230	238	97	85	115	113	211	209	208	118	206	120	121	204	45	280	295	30	2925	
87	95	228	240	210	212	114	116	117	207	119	205	123	202	55	270	29	296	2925	
227	98	108	217	137	188	161	166	155	168	173	152	203	122	48	277	42	283	2925	
239	86	109	216	187	138	156	167	162	165	171	154	201	124	273	52	282	43	2925	
91	234	106	219	139	186	170	157	164	159	179	146	200	125	46	279	40	285	2925	
233	92	101	224	185	140	163	160	169	158	153	172	126	199	278	47	38	287	2925	
235	90	223	102	184	141	148	147	180	174	150	176	198	127	53	272	41	284	2925	
94	231	221	104	182	143	177	178	145	151	149	175	128	197	275	50	281	44	2925	
236	89	214	111	144	181	129	195	131	193	136	134	190	192	292	31	290	37	2925	
226	99	103	222	142	183	196	130	194	132	189	191	135	133	33	294	288	35	2925	
88	237	218	107	64	261	252	75	74	79	84	249	243	81	245	78	242	248	2925	
96	229	220	105	265	60	73	250	251	246	241	76	82	244	80	247	83	77	2925	
100	225	112	213	61	65	71	70	263	258	58	253	266	257	63	268	66	256	2925	
93	232	215	110	260	264	254	255	62	67	267	72	59	68	262	57	259	69	2925	
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

For more examples of similar kind with pdf file for download refer the author’s site <https://shorturl.at/KXY47>.

Acknowledgement

The examples considered in the work are considered using different softwares by H. White [1]. The author is thankful to H. White for providing these softwares.

5 Author’s Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers

For author’s contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

References

[1] **H. White**, Bordered Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/Download.html>

• Block-Wise Magic Squares

[2] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Constructions of Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 8 to 108, May 15, 2019, pp. 1-43, **Zenodo**, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2843326>.

[3] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Equal Sums Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order $4k$, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-17, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554288>.

[4] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Rectangles in Construction of Block-Wise Pandiagonal Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-49, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554520>.

[5] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Equal Sums Magic Squares of Orders $3k$ and $6k$, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554895>.

[6] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Unequal Sums Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-52, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555260>.

[7] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 12 to 36, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-53, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555343>.

[8] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 39 to 45, **Zenodo**, February 2, 2019, pp. 1-73, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555889>.

• Bordered Magic Squares

[9] **Inder J. Taneja**, Nested Magic Squares With Perfect Square Sums, Pythagorean Triples, and Borders Differences, **Zenodo**, June 14, 2019, pp. 1-59, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3246586>.

- [10] **Inder J. Taneja**, Symmetric Properties of Nested Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, June 29, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3262170>.
- [11] **Inder J. Taneja**, General Sum Symmetric and Positive Entries Nested Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, July 04, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3268877>.
- [12] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered Magic Squares With Order Square Magic Sums, **Zenodo**, January 20, 2020, pp. 1-26, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3613690>.
- [13] **Inder J. Taneja**, Fractional and Decimal Type Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2020. **Zenodo**, January 20, 2020, pp.1-25. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3613698>.
- [14] **Inder J. Taneja**, Fractional and Decimal Type Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2021, **Zenodo**, December 16, 2020, pp. 1-33, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4327333>.
- [15] **Inder J. Taneja**, Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2022, **Zenodo**, December 28, 2021, pp. 1-38, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5807789>

• **Block-Bordered Magic Squares**

- [16] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - I, **Zenodo**, August 18, 2020, pp. 1-81, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3990291>.
- [17] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - II, **Zenodo**, August 18, 2020, pp. 1-90, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3990293>.
- [18] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - III, **Zenodo**, September 01, 2020, pp. 1-93, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4011213>.

• Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic Squares

- [19] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic and Bimagic Squares With Magic Sums 21, 21^2 and 2021. **Zenodo**, December 16, 2020, pp. 1-118, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4380343>.
- [20] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 10 to 47. **Zenodo**, January 14, 2021, pp. 1-185, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4437783>.
- [21] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered and Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares: Odd Order Multiples, **Zenodo**, February 10, 2021, pp. 1-75, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4527739>
- [22] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered and Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares: Even Order Multiples, **Zenodo**, February 10, 2021, pp. 1-96, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4527746>

• Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of Even Order Magic Squares

- [23] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Bordered and Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 4, **Zenodo**, August 31, 2021, pp. 1-148, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5347897>.
- [24] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 6, **Zenodo**, July 25, 2023, pp. 1-32, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8184983>.
- [25] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered and Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 8, **Zenodo**, July 26, 2023, pp. 1-58, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8187791>.
- [26] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 10, **Zenodo**, July 26, pp. 1-40, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8187888>.
- [27] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered and Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 12, **Zenodo**, July 27, 2023, pp. 1-31, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8188293>.
- [28] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 14, **Zenodo**, July 27, pp. 1-33, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8188395>.

[29] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered and Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 16, **Zenodo**, July 27, pp. 1-30, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8190884>.

[30] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 18, **Zenodo**, July 28, pp. 1-31, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8191223>.

[31] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered and Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 20, **Zenodo**, July 28, pp. 1-45, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8191426>.

• Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of Odd Order Magic Squares

[32] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Bordered and Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 3, **Zenodo**, May 05, pp. 1-29, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898383>.

[33] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered and Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 5, **Zenodo**, July 23, 2023, pp. 1-36, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8175759>.

[34] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered and Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 7, **Zenodo**, July 23, pp. 1-34, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8176061>.

[35] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 9, **Zenodo**, July 23, 2023, pp. 1-28, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8176357>.

[36] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 11, **Zenodo**, July 24, pp. 1-34, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8176475>.

[37] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 13, **Zenodo**, July 24, pp. 1-32, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8178879>.

[38] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 15, **Zenodo**, July 24, pp. 1-35, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8178935>.

[39] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 17, **Zenodo**, July 25, pp. 1-26, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8180706>.

[40] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 19, **Zenodo**, July 25, pp. 1-31, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8180919>.

• Magic Squares With Bordered Magic Rectangles

- [41] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Styles of Magic Squares of Orders 6, 8, 10 and 12 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, November 14, 2022, pp. 1-26, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7319985>.
- [42] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Styles of Magic Squares of Order 14 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, November 14, 2022, pp. 1-40, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7319787>.
- [43] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Styles of Magic Squares of Order 16 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, November 14, 2022, pp. 1-63, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7320116>.
- [44] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Styles of Magic Squares of Order 18 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, November 14, 2022, pp. 1-85, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7320131>.
- [45] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Styles of Magic Squares of Order 20 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, November 14, 2022, pp. 1-88, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7320877>.
- [46] **Inder J. Taneja**, Few Examples of Magic Squares of Even Orders 6 to 18 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, October 19, 2022, pp. 1-30, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7225854>.
- [47] **Inder J. Taneja**, Few Examples of Magic Squares of Even Orders 20 to 30 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, October 19, 2022, pp. 1-100, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7225886>.
- [48] **Inder J. Taneja**, Single Crossed Bordered Magic Rectangles and Magic Squares of Order 40, **Zenodo**, January 24, 2023, pp. 1-76, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7565946>
- [49] **Inder J. Taneja**, Double Crossed Bordered Magic Rectangles and Magic Squares of Order 40, **Zenodo**, January 30, 2023, pp. 1-102, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7585787>
- [50] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Order 42 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, March 03, 2023, pp. 1-92, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7695834>.

- [51] **Inder J. Taneja**, Single-Cross Bordered Magic Rectangles and Magic Squares of Order 42, **Zenodo**, March 03, 2023, pp. 1-69, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7695939>
- [52] **Inder J. Taneja**, Double-Cross Bordered Magic Rectangles and Magic Squares of Order 42, **Zenodo**, March 03, 2023, pp. 1-59, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7696070>.
- [53] **Inder J. Taneja**, Closed Double-Cross Bordered Magic Rectangles and Magic Squares of Order 42, **Zenodo**, March 03, 2023, pp. 1-28, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7696181>.
- [54] **Inder J. Taneja**, 8000+ Magic Squares of Order 22 in Different Styles, Models and Designs, **Zenodo**, April 08, pp. 1-135, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7809478>.

• Figured Magic Squares and Bordered Magic Rectangles

- [55] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Orders 6, 10, 12, 14 and 16 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, November 29, 2022, pp. 1-31, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377674>.
- [56] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Orders 18 and 20 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, November 29, 2022, pp. 1-87, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377689>.
- [57] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 22 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, November 29, 2022, pp. 1-61, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377706>.
- [58] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 24 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, November 29, 2022, pp. 1-104, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377779>.
- [59] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 26 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, November 29, 2022, pp. 1-88, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377794>.
- [60] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 28 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, December 02, 2022, pp. 1-179, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7390666>.

- [61] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 30 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, December 02, 2022, pp. 1-179, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7390705>.
- [62] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 32 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, December 22, 2022, pp. 1-310, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7472891>.
- [63] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 34 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, December 27, 2022, pp. 1-193, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7486540>.
- [64] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 36 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, December 27, 2022, pp. 1-140, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7486548>.
- [65] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 38 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, January 03, 2023, pp. 1-133, <https://doi.org/110.5281/zenodo.7500188>.
- [66] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 40 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, January 03, 2023, pp. 1-157, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7500192>.

• Double Digits Bordered Magic Squares

- [67] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 4: Orders 8 to 24, **Zenodo**, April, 26, 2023, pp. 1-43, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7866956>.
- [68] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 28 and 32, **Zenodo**, April, 26, 2023, pp. 1-36, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7866981>.
- [69] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 10, 14, 18 and 22, **Zenodo**, April, 30, 2023, pp. 1-43, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7880931>.
- [70] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 26 and 30, **Zenodo**, April, 30, 2023, pp. 1-45, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7880937>.

[71] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 36 and 40, **Zenodo**, May, 04, 2023, pp. 1-41, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7896709>.

[72] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 34 and 38, **Zenodo**, May 10, 2023, pp. 1-45, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7922571>.

• Odd Order Magic Squares

[73] **Inder J. Taneja**, Odd Order Magic Squares: Orders 3 to 15, **Zenodo**, June 15, 2023, pp. 1-43, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8043030>.

[74] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Orders 17 and 19, **Zenodo**, June 15, 2023, pp. 1-38, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8043105>.

[75] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Orders 21 and 23, **Zenodo**, June 15, 2023, pp. 1-43, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8043198>.

[76] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Order 25, **Zenodo**, June 15, 2023, pp. 1-27, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8043228>.

[77] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Order 27, **Zenodo**, August 06, 2023, pp. 1-32, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8218291>.

[78] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Order 29, **Zenodo**, August 06, 2023, pp. 1-30, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8218771>.

[79] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Order 31, **Zenodo**, August 06, 2023, pp. 1-35, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8219053>.

[80] **Inder J. Taneja**, Double Digits Even and Odd Orders Bordered Magic Squares - Summary, <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=9406>.

[81] **Inder J. Taneja**, New Concepts in Magic Squares: Double Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 7 to 108, **Zenodo**, August 09, 2023, pp. 1-30, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8230214>.

• Cornered Magic Squares

[82] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares of Order 6, **Zenodo**, May 23, 2023, pp. 1-23, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7960679>.

- [83] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 5 to 13, **Zenodo**, June 03, 2023, pp. 1-71, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8000467>.
- [84] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 14 to 24, **Zenodo**, June 03, 2023, pp. 1-39, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8000471>.
- [85] **Inder J. Taneja**, New Concepts in Magic Squares: Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 5 to 81, **Zenodo**, August 09, 2023, pp. 1-27, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8231157>.

• Magic Squares with Cornered Magic Rectangles

- [86] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Types of Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, September 04, 2023, pp. 1-26, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8316719>.
- [87] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Types of Magic Rectangles in Construction of Magic Squares of Orders 14 and 18, **Zenodo**, September 10, 2023, pp. 1-32, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8331709>.
- [88] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Types of Magic Rectangles in Construction of Magic Squares of Order 22, **Zenodo**, September 10, 2023, pp. 1-36, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8331743>.
- [89] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Types of Magic Rectangles in Construction of Magic Squares of Order 26, **Zenodo**, September 10, 2023, pp. 1-39, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8331750>.
- [90] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Types of Magic Rectangles in Construction of Magic Squares of Order 30, **Zenodo**, September 10, 2023, pp. 1-44, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8331755>.
- [91] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Types of Magic Rectangles in Construction of Magic Squares of Order 34, **Zenodo**, September 10, 2023, pp. 1-49, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8331759>.
- [92] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares in Construction of Magic Squares of Orders 16, 20, 24 and 28, **Zenodo**, September 10, 2023, pp. 1-35, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8332156>.

• Creative Magic Squares

[93] **Inder J. Taneja**, Creative Magic Squares: Area Representations, **Zenodo**, June 22, pp. 1-45, 2021,
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5009224>.

[94] **Inder J. Taneja**, Creative Magic Squares: Area Representations with Fraction Numbers Entries (Version 2), **Zenodo**, August 16, 2021,
1-77, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5209502>.
